

**A STUDY USEFULNESS OF COMPUTER APPLICATIONS OAASIS IN ACADEMIC
ADMINISTRATION AMONG COLLEGES AFFILIATED TO NORTH
MAHARASHTRA UNIVERSITY, JALGAON**

Mr. Milind V. Bildikar,

B.P. Arts, S.M.A. Science & K.K.C. Commerce College, Chalisgaon

Abstract:-

E-governance has enabled universities to spread their current geographical reach, to interact to prospective students all around the world and to establish themselves as global education providers. Now a days most of the colleges in Maharashtra are using Computers and I.C.T. in Academic Administrations. The North Maharashtra University is also using Computer application for Academic Administration. The University is using OAASIS. A survey is made to find out the usefulness of OAASIS among the colleges. How effectively the College Nonteaching staff are using OAASIS for administration purpose. Majority of people i. e 57.8% rated as Good

Introduction:-

E-governance is the process of service delivery and information providing tool to citizens by using Computers and I.C.T. The effective use of I.C.T services in administration of colleges can greatly improve efficiencies, transparency, accuracy and also reduce communication costs,

The Maharashtra Knowledge Corporation Limited (MKCL) had developed a Computer Application Online Academic Administration System and Information Services (OAASIS) for Academic Administration among colleges and Universities of Maharashtra State. The North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon and all affiliated colleges are using OAASIS. It is expected that the Nonteaching staff of Colleges and Institutes Should make use of OAASIS for administrative purpose. The present study focus on how effectively the Nonteaching staff of Colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University is using OAASIS for academic administration purpose then What is the usefulness of computer application in academic administration and how effectively the Nonteaching staff of Colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University is using OAASIS for academic administration purpose and What is the usefulness of computer application in academic administration?

Material and Method :-

During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. Primary data is collected from various Teachers associated with colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University with the help of structured questionnaire. The research practices are comprise of random sampling,

data collection, data editing, data classification, tabulation and interpretation of data with the help of statistical tools. Both primary data and secondary data collected.

Observation and result-

Table 1: How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online affiliation?

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online affiliation?	Very Good	44	43.1
	Good	54	52.9
	Average	4	3.9

Figure 1 : How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online affiliation?

Table 2: How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online examination?

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online examination?	Very Good	37	36.3
	Good	55	53.9
	Average	10	9.8

**Table 2: How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online examination?
Frequency**

Figure 2 : How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online examination?

Table 3: How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online Staff Approval?

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online Staff Approval?	Very Good	29	28.4
	Good	59	57.8
	Average	10	9.8
	Poor	4	3.9

**Table 3: How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online Staff Approval?
Frequency**

Figure 3 : How do you rate OAASIS framework for Online Staff Approval?

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(UGC Approved Journal No 48178, 48818)

ISSN 2278-5655

The responses of Nonteaching Administrative staff when they requested to rate OAASIS framework for online affiliation - 43.1% means rated as Very Good, Majority 52.9% rated as Good whereas only 3.9% means rated as Average.

The above table shows the responses of Nonteaching Administrative staff when they requested to rate OAASIS framework for online examination – 36.3% rated as Very Good, Majority 53.9% Heads rated as good whereas only 9.8% rated as Average.

The above table shows the responses of Nonteaching Administrative staff when they requested to rate OAASIS framework for Online Staff Approval – 28.4 rated as Very Good, Majority 57.8% rated as Good, 9.8% rated as Average and only 3.9% rated as Poor.

Discussion: it is observed that majority of Nonteaching Administrative staff are using Computer application in academic administration. Majority of Nonteaching Administrative staff are satisfied with OAASIS. To increase the effective use of OAASIS, it is recommended to provide training to Nonteaching staff.

Refrences:-

MKCL. (2014). Retrieved April 17, 2015, from www.mkcl.org.

Mohan, D. A. (2012). e-Governance in education system - knowledge management based economy. *Abhinav National Monthly Referred Journal in Commerce and Management* .

OASIS. (2011). Retrieved Jan 14, 2014, from www.nmu.ac.in: <http://www.nmu.ac.in>

Open educational resorces K-12 education in India . (2013). *ICT for school education conference, Min of HRD* .